

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF CARRYING OUT INTERNAL AUDIT OF CYBER SECURITY AND ITS USE IN THE ACTIVITIES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS

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Abstract

The article examines the foreign experience of conducting an internal audit of cybersecurity in banks, as well as its use in the activities of Russian banks.

Despite the significant attention of banks to the study of the types of cyber threats, the reasons for their occurrence, the threat landscape is constantly evolving, leading to a more complex cyber ecosystem, and the consequences of the implementation of cyber threats will exponentially increase. This is primarily due to the development of digital infrastructure, the introduction of financial technologies and the active activity of FinTech firms, blurring the boundaries between traditional banking and non-banking services, exacerbating competition and creating new sources of threats to the cybersecurity of banks. The problem will be aggravated by the fact that banking information systems will become more interconnected, operational processes more automated, while the existing infrastructure of information and communication technologies has not been developed with a cybersecurity priority, which will require its adaptation to new business conditions.

In view of this, the formation of measures to prevent the occurrence of situations classified as a cyber threat or fraud is an important scientific and applied task.

Keywords: internal audit, bank, cyber threat, cybersecurity, mechanism, international experience, security.

Currently, the banking and financial services sector is the most attractive for cyber-attacks and cyber fraud due to the potential for significant financial and non-financial benefits for attackers.

According to statistics, the financial sector in 2021 was attacked 65% more often than any other, while in 2021 28.5% of reported information leakage incidents were recorded in the financial sector, and financial institutions were affected by these incidents 30 times more often than firms in other industries. At the same time, hackers stole almost 4 billion rubles from clients of Russian banks in the third quarter of 2022. This is about 24% more than a year earlier [2].

Despite the significant attention of banks to the study of types of cyber threats, the reasons for their appearance, the threat landscape is constantly evolving, leading to the launch of an essentially more complex cyber ecosystem, and the consequences of the implementation of cyber threats will increase exponentially. This is primarily due to the development of digital infrastructure, the introduction of financial technologies and the active activity of FinTech firms, blurring the boundaries between traditional banking and non-banking services, intensifying competition and creating new sources of threats to the cybersecurity of banks. The problem will be exacerbated by the fact that banking information systems will become more interconnected, operational processes will become more automated, while the existing information and communication technology infrastructure has not been designed with cybersecurity as a priority, which will require its adaptation to the new operating conditions.

In view of this, the formation of measures to prevent the onset of situations classified as a cyber threat or fraud is an important scientific and applied task.

A significant contribution to the formation and development of the theoretical and methodological found-

ations of internal audit in banks, on which developments in the field of internal audit of cybersecurity should be based, was made by such domestic and foreign scientists as: S.N. Malofeev [1], D.V. Romanchenko [4], G.V. Semeko [5], P.V. Revenkov, A.A. Berdyugin [3] and others.

At the same time, despite the fact that the problem of cybersecurity in the banking sector has been fully and comprehensively considered in the scientific literature, there are practically no comprehensive theoretical developments substantiating the system of internal cybersecurity audit as a preventive component in the cybersecurity system of the bank in the domestic scientific literature.

At the same time, foreign researchers [6-9] have more experience in organizing and justifying banking cybersecurity systems based on the use of an internal audit mechanism.

Thus, the purpose of this study is to substantiate the possibilities of using the internal audit mechanism in ensuring the cybersecurity of a commercial bank based on foreign experience in this area of banking.

Based on the goal, we will formulate the basic concepts that define the internal audit system as an inseparable component of bank cybersecurity, which is a set of interrelated elements (goals, tasks, object, subject, mechanism) that operate on the basis of general and special principles and allow an objective assessment of the level security and preservation of the properties of information assets and information infrastructure of the bank under the constant influence of external and / or internal threats, as well as compliance with the requirements of national and international legislation.

The objects of internal audit are information assets - tangible or intangible objects that are information or contain information that serve to process, store or transmit information and are of value to the bank.

As foreign authors point out [7, 9], in order to form an internal audit object environment in the bank's cybersecurity system, it is necessary to consider the

threats generated by both the external and internal environment (Table 1).

Table 1.

Classification of bank cybersecurity threats.

FEATURE	TYPE OF THREAT
By source	- Internal (loss, destruction, theft, distortion or disclosure of information, information leakage); - external (content modification, confidentiality violation, logical integrity violation, information property rights violation, physical integrity violation, natural and man-made disasters that disrupt the normal operation of information systems, etc.)
By etiology	- Objective (natural), characterized by the influence on the object of protection of physical processes or natural phenomena that are not dependent on a person; - subjective, characterized by the influence of human activity on the object of protection; - results of social engineering (phishing, pharming, pretexting, screaming, etc.).
By the degree of impact on the information system.	- Passive, without affecting the state of the information system; - active, with a violation of the normal process of functioning of the information system of the bank.
By purposefulness.	- Unintentional (false, accidental, thoughtless, without malicious intent and selfish purposes) actions of personnel and users of banking services; - intentional (for mercenary purposes, under duress by third parties, with malicious intent, etc.) actions of personnel, users of banking services, criminal groups and formations, political and economic structures, as well as individuals.

Also, according to Majdalawieh M., University Z., Zaghloul I. [7], an increase in the number of operational processes, including key ones, transferred to third parties (for example, Internet providers, equipment installation contractors), leads to an increase in dependence banks from cybersecurity counterparties. In response, the bank should have the ability to audit the cybersecurity of third parties to ensure that their activities meet established standards and do not pose a threat to cybersecurity.

The internal audit services of the bank, which are formed in all foreign banks and which, among other things, audit the cybersecurity system, are involved in

the implementation of the tasks of the internal audit of cybersecurity.

It should be noted that the internal audit service is the third line of defense against cyber risks, while not directly involved in managing them. Its role is directly reduced to assessing the adequacy of the cybersecurity system to the goals and objectives of the bank, assessing the overall effectiveness of the actions performed by the first and second lines of defense (information security management units, respectively) in managing and reducing cybersecurity risks.

The relationship between the subjects of bank cybersecurity and the internal audit service is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. - Model for conducting an internal audit of the cybersecurity system of a commercial bank.

Therefore, an internal cybersecurity audit should focus on evaluating the effectiveness of the cybersecurity system in order to determine whether it is consistent with the strategy and objectives of the bank in the market in the current conditions of the cyber ecosystem.

To achieve these goals, a significant number of multidirectional tasks should be performed, namely:

- check the compliance of the existing cybersecurity policy with the current legislation, international standards and recommendations;
- identify shortcomings and evaluate the effectiveness of the bank's cybersecurity policy, internal banking standards, regulations and procedures;
- assess the current level of security of the bank's information assets;
- conduct an analysis of the risks associated with the possibility of implementing cybersecurity threats against information assets;
- evaluate the effectiveness of cyber risk management;
- based on the results of analytical work, identify possible vulnerabilities of the bank's information assets to external and internal threats to the loss of cybersecurity;
- examine the existing cybersecurity controls for operational, administrative and managerial aspects, ensure the effective implementation of cybersecurity norms and compliance with established cybersecurity standards;
- to develop recommendations for introducing new and improving the effectiveness of existing mechanisms for ensuring cybersecurity.

The achievement of these goals and objectives is ensured through the creation and continuous modernization of the internal cybersecurity audit mechanism.

Summarizing the developments of scientists, we propose to define the internal audit mechanism in the field of cybersecurity as a set of methodological, methodological and technical subsystems that ensure the identification and structuring of objects, setting goals and objectives, choosing methods and procedures to obtain sufficient and appropriate audit evidence that allows arguing conclusions and recommendations. to ensure the required level of cybersecurity.

This mechanism should work on the basis of a system of internal audit principles. However, the general principles of internal audit remain important.

When structuring the principles, we consider it appropriate to single out:

- fundamental principles that reflect the essence of internal audit as a social phenomenon (theoretical component): independence, objectivity;
 - consistency, complexity, competence;
 - efficiency;
- methodological principles that form the basis of his practice:
 - a) principles of professional ethics: honesty; objectivity; confidentiality; professional competence;
 - b) principles of organization: systematic; efficiency; planning; balance; documentation; communication [6].

In addition to the above principles, it is also advisable to consider more specific audit-oriented principles in the bank's cybersecurity system:

- relevance: compliance of the internal audit mechanism with the current regulatory framework, international recommendations and standards, and the cyber ecosystem;
- completeness: the audit should cover all objects and areas of cybersecurity audit, consider all threats and factors that may affect the effectiveness of the bank's cybersecurity mechanism;
- reliability: the existing subsystems of the internal audit mechanism allow for a consistent assessment of cyber risks or measurements of the audited object and substantiate audit conclusions;
- frequency in accordance with the objectives of internal audit: an effective internal audit system should provide for the possibility of conducting preliminary, regular, occasional and non-working audits.

Based on the results of a study of foreign audit practice, it was revealed that the landscape of the cyber ecosystem is constantly changing, creating new threats to the loss of cyber security of banks and leading to an increase in the level of cyber risks. Under these conditions, banks must have an effective cybersecurity system in place to address existing and potential external and internal threats.

An important role in preventing cyber threats is played by internal audit, which gives an objective assessment of the current level of cyber security in the bank, identifies weaknesses in the cyber security and cyber risk management system and makes recommendations for their elimination.

An internal cybersecurity audit is defined as a periodic system for collecting and evaluating information to determine whether all of the bank's systems provide an appropriate state of security of information assets and information infrastructure, maintaining the properties of information assets (availability, integrity or confidentiality) at a target level in accordance with established criteria in conditions constant influence of external and/or internal threats in compliance with the requirements of national and international legislation.

Thus, we conclude that the cybersecurity internal audit system is a set of interrelated elements (goals and objectives, object, subject, mechanism) that operate on the basis of general and special principles and allow an objective assessment of the level of security and preservation of the properties of information assets and information infrastructure of the bank under the constant influence of external and / or internal threats, as well as compliance with the requirements of national and international legislation.

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DIRECTIONS FOR THE USE OF DIGITAL COMMERCIAL MODELS IN THE ORGANIZATION OF GOODS MOVEMENT

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Abstract

This scientific article analyzes the essence of electronic trade and electronic commerce, the essence of 6 models of calculation and interaction. The importance of e-commerce or e-commerce models in the organization of goods movement, the mechanism of operation was studied.

Keywords: "G2C", "B2C" "B2B", "G2B", e-commerce, e-purchase, online shopping.

Introduction

It is difficult to imagine the competitiveness of sectors and sectors of the economy where the principles of the digital economy have not penetrated. Along with the digitization of the commodity market and the activities of its structures, at a time when the "Industry-4.0" program is being widely implemented in the world economy, the digitization of marketing research of the commodity market is important in increasing the sales volume of enterprises and organizations, as well as in bringing the seller and the buyer closer together.

Currently, the basis of the achievements in the economy, especially in the field of entrepreneurship, is the highly developed and effective use of information technologies in various segments. The economy of our republic is no exception to this situation, of course. Because the development of information technologies is of great importance in ensuring new economic relations.

As a result of the gradual development of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the importance of new principles of business activity, especially electronic commerce, has greatly increased. By now, every internet user has tried to understand the meaning of the word e-commerce.

According to the evaluation of the world's independent "eMarketer" agency, the turnover of consumer goods in the world in 2021 will be 22,492 trillion. amounted to US dollars, of which 1.3 trillion. part of it corresponded to internet trade, that is, it made up 5.9% of the total turnover of consumer goods, and China and the USA were its leaders. It is recognized that in 2021, the share of these countries in the total electronic trade of the world will be 55 percent.

It should also be noted that there are over 3.4 billion e-commerce users worldwide. Although China

is the leader in e-commerce, the biggest markets are Germany and Great Britain. According to forecasts, between 2020 and 2027, the volume of e-commerce will grow by 14.7% and generate revenue of 27.15 trillion dollars [1].

In such a positive trend, effective organization of goods movement is also important. In particular, the increasing number of digital technologies, systems and tools creates the possibility of wide application of digital commercial models in organizing the movement of goods. From this point of view, the research of this topic is of urgent importance.

Literature review

The issues of effective management of the movement of goods in the conditions of the innovative economy have been extensively researched in the scientific works of foreign scientists. In particular, C.J.Langley researched the application of the digital economy methodology in the organization of goods movement. K.Oliver and M.Webber formed the concept of business logistics as an integral tool of business management in the organization of the movement of commodity resources, and also showed that there are significant principle differences in the functions of marketing and logistics in distribution channels [2]. In the early 1980s, the term "Supply Chain Management" began to be used in the United States. The first use of this term was proposed by the American designer K.Oliver and M.Webber as part of an integrated strategy, calling it the delivery of primary raw materials to production enterprises, the management of supply chains from production enterprises to the final consumer [3].

Chairman Hugh MacKeown has researched that the wholesale trade is the main factor in organizing the movement of goods [4]. In his research, it was